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Gu Zimo

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The Eastern Echo of the Thinking of Being: A Study of Zao Wou-Ki's Painting from the Perspectives of Heidegger and Taoism

Gu Zimo

Abstract

This paper focuses on the art of Zao Wou-Ki, interpreting it through the dual perspectives of Martin Heidegger's philosophy of Being and Taoist thought. In response to the current lack of application of cross-cultural philosophical dialogue in the field of art, and the fact that existing studies on Zao Wou-Ki tend to emphasize stylistic analysis rather than philosophical depth, this research aims to reveal that Zao Wou-Ki's abstract paintings visually articulate both Heidegger's ontological difference and the Taoist notion of mysterious unity, thereby demonstrating the universality of fundamental issues in the aesthetics of art.

Key Words

Art Aesthetics, Heidegger, *Tao Te Ching*, Zao Wou-Ki

Martin Heidegger deconstructed Western metaphysics using a phenomenological approach, yet in his later years, he candidly admitted “Our thinking is not yet prepared to truly listen to the voice of Being.” This predicament had already been foreseen in the *Tao Te Ching*: “Those who know do not speak; those who speak do not know” (Chapter 56)—when art attempts to capture Being through form, Being has already quietly slipped away through the clefts between language and image. It is worth noting that in his later years, Heidegger collaborated with Paul Shih-Yi Hsiao on translating the *Tao Te Ching*. Although the project remained unfinished, it planted the seeds of Eastern wisdom in his philosophical thought.¹ The German sinologist Rudolf G. Wagner pointed out that Heidegger's reception of Taoist thought was based on a profound recognition of the crisis in Western philosophy.² The contemporary significance of this cross-cultural dialogue lies in the following: when technological rationality reduces Being to a calculable object, the integration of the Taoist tradition of the mystical mirror (*xuan jian*) with phenomenology may offer new possibilities for safeguarding the truth of Being.

Zao Wou-Ki (1920–2013) was a preeminent contem-

porary Chinese-French painter, renowned for his distinctive style of abstract expressionism. His artistic career bridged Eastern and Western traditions, evolving from early figurative painting toward abstraction, and integrating the lyrical essence of traditional Chinese ink wash painting with the techniques of Western modernism. Works such as his series of *Untitled pieces* and *Homage to Cézanne* (figure 1) not only demonstrate a fusion of color and form but also embody profound philosophical reflections on existence, nature, and time. Deeply influenced by the *Tao Te Ching*, Zao Wou-Ki once collaborated with his close friend, the French abstract painter Henri Michaux, on a translation of the text. Their mutual exchange profoundly shaped each other's artistic vision. Zao Wou-Ki remarked “I have always loved Laozi. My grandfather also leaned toward Taoism. I do not paint to express something, but to let the painting speak for itself.”³ This reveals his artistic philosophy and also forms a striking resonance with Heidegger's concept of letting beings be. Through the lens of Zao Wou-Ki's paintings, this paper will delve into how his work embodies the philosophical consonance between Heidegger and the *Tao Te Ching* across the dimensions of ontology, critique of technology, and the aesthetics of void and whiteness.

Figure 1. Zao Wou-Ki, *Homage to Cézanne 06.11.05-Diptych*, 2005, oil on canvas, 162x260cm.

In this context the artistic practice of Zao Wou-Ki, as a painter who integrated Eastern and Western artistic traditions, becomes particularly significant. This paper argues that Zao Wou-Ki's work fully embodies a profound dialogue between Heidegger's philosophy of Being and Taoist aesthetics. Through abstract forms, the use of void and whiteness, and a deep contemplation of nature and existence, his paintings offer a way to directly experience Being that transcends language and conceptualization. In recent years, cross-cultural philosophical dialogue in the field of art has continued to deepen. Western scholarship's interpretation of Zao Wou-Ki highlights his global significance; the French scholar François Cheng emphasized the "poetics of the void" in Zao Wou-Ki's paintings, arguing that he transformed the Taoist concept of non-action (*wu wei*) into an abstract visual language. Cheng noted that Zao Wou-Ki's work "establishes order within chaos, transcending the limitations of Western abstraction."⁴ In 1966, French critic Jean Lescure and Zao Wou-Ki decided to collaborate on creating prints; Lescure remarked: "The forms in Zao Wou-Ki's work are dazzlingly radiant, their substance profoundly rich, leaving an enduring impression. With an ever-increasing freedom and passion, they embody a seamless fusion of East and West, of strength and contemplation."⁵ The

German phenomenologist Günter Figal, applying Heidegger's concept of *Dasein* to analyze Zao Wou-Ki's works, describes his canvases as a "clearing for the disclosure of Being."⁶ Based on this, the present study aims to address the core question: how Zao Wou-Ki's paintings, through their abstract forms, application of void and whiteness, and profound contemplation of nature, visually articulate the dialogue between Heidegger's ontological difference and the Taoist idea of mysterious unity (*xuan tong*), thereby offering an artistic pathway to safeguard the truth of Being in the technological age. Methodologically, this paper adopts a comparative aesthetic framework, integrating textual and visual analysis to examine the philosophical intertextuality within his works.

1. Ontological Difference and Mysterious Unity: Visual Manifestations in Zao Wou-Ki's Paintings

Heidegger's subversion of Western philosophy began with his profound revelation of the ontological difference. In *Being and Time*, with an almost incisive rigor, he critiqued traditional metaphysics, accusing it of conflating the fundamental distinction between Being (*Sein*) and Beings (*Seiendes*).⁷ This conflation is akin to

mistaking the illumination of light for the light source itself, thereby obscuring the true focus of philosophical inquiry. Heidegger argued that from Plato in ancient Greece to Hegel in the modern era, the history of Western philosophy has almost entirely become a history of the forgetting of Being. Plato's theory of Forms regarded the Form of the Good as the highest idea, while Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel's Absolute Spirit attempted to encompass the movement and development of all beings through dialectics. Yet these efforts remained at the level of questioning why beings exist, without ever truly touching upon the meaning of Being itself.⁸ Heidegger pointed out that traditional metaphysics consistently tends to interpret Being as some supreme being or abstract essence—such as God, reason, or spirit—while overlooking Being as the primordial ground and context through which all beings manifest. To rectify this deviation, he introduced the renowned question of Being (Seinsfrage), seeking to liberate philosophy from its fixation on beings and reorient thought toward confronting the self-disclosing of Being itself. This inquiry not only reshapes philosophical methodology but also issues a fundamental summons to reconfigure humanity's very mode of thinking.⁹

This revolutionary insight unexpectedly finds a profound resonance in the distant Eastern philosophy of Taoism. Laozi states at the very beginning of the *Tao Te Ching*'s first Chapter: "The Tao that can be spoken is not the eternal Tao." Laozi reminds us that the true Tao transcends any language or definition; once confined by words, it ceases to be the authentic Tao. This aligns seamlessly with Heidegger's understanding of Being—it, too, is not an object that can be captured by metaphysical concepts but must be revealed beyond the boundaries of language through a mode of expression closer to poetry. Zhuangzi further deepens this idea with the parable of "The Cook Ding Butchering an Ox." When butchering the ox, Cook Ding no longer relies on visual observation or intellectual calculation but instead depends on an intuition described as "meeting it with spirit, not looking with eyes." He reaches a state where "perception ceases and spirit moves freely." His knife follows the natural grain of the ox's body, completing the task with effortless grace. This pinnacle of skill embodies the natural flow of the Tao emerging when the cognitive subject is suspended.¹⁰ This state shares similarities with what Heidegger termed the condition of Dasein in the process of disclosing Being. However, Taoism goes a step further: through the loss of self (*sang wo*), it dissolves subjectivity entirely, allowing the manifestation of Being to occur without relying on a

presupposed receiver of meaning.

François Cheng, in the exhibition catalogue for *Zao Wou-Ki* at the Grand Palais in Paris, noted: "Through the rhythmic movement of the brush, the Chinese artist immerses their entire being into the act of writing, enabling each character to carry both the cosmic breath (*qi*) and the inner principles of all things. This artistic practice, employing core concepts of Chinese cosmology such as void and solidity (*xu shi*) and light-dark forces (*yin yang*), transcends mere aesthetic creation to construct an intermediary field where true life can be realized—becoming a lived philosophy."¹¹ The cosmological emphasis on void in Chinese thought, which highlights the dialectical relationship between writing and life forms while pursuing the harmony between ink-brush expression and life's rhythms, profoundly influenced Zao Wou-Ki. Thus, Chinese cosmology became a vital reference in his creative practice. As the French writer Alain Jouffroy observed in *Art*: "Zao Wou-Ki's work clearly demonstrates how Chinese cosmology has become a global modern expression—it is not an object of meditation, but a reflection of the meditative spirit. Diverse artists such as Paul Klee, Mark Tobey, and Henri Michaux have all drawn upon this intellectual tradition."¹²

In the realm of art, Zao Wou-Ki's paintings offer a visual manifestation of this philosophical dialogue. His abstract works, such as *10.01.68* (figure 2), create an undifferentiated state of being through the fusion of colors and the fluidity of forms. The canvas contains no distinct subject or object; instead, lines and color patches diffuse like mist and clouds, evoking the primordial truth of existence. This approach transcends traditional painting's reliance on figurative representation, allowing viewers to confront directly the self-disclosing of Being. Zao Wou-Ki once stated "My painting is part of nature, not an imitation of it." This resonates deeply with Heidegger's call to let beings be, while also echoing the Taoist ideal of losing the self—by dissolving subjectivity, existence is allowed to speak for itself.

Taking *Untitled* (1972) as an example (figure 3), the interplay of deep and light ink tones alongside expansive areas of blank space presents a dynamic equilibrium. The white canvas base symbolizes non-being or void, while the application of black ink represents being or substance. The arrangement of ink masses and lines does not depict figurative objects but instead creates a sense of dynamic balance through variations in density and spacing. The densely concentrated ink on the left suggests solidity and gathering, gradually transitioning toward the right into lighter, fragmented brushstrokes and flying white (*fei bai*) effects, embodying emptiness

Figure 2. Zao Wou-Ki, *10.01.68*, 1968, oil on canvas, 82×116.5cm.

and dispersion. This composition of interwoven void and substance not only aligns with the Taoist philosophy of the mutual generation of yin and yang but also mimics the ceaseless vitality of nature through the fluidity of ink—evoking the flow of clouds or the transformation of mountains and rivers—thereby conveying the profound artistic conception (*yi jing*) of the cosmos and the primordial power of nature. Furthermore, the rhythm of the brushstrokes, with their pauses and accelerations, and the *fei bai* effect resonate with the Taoist concept of governing through non-action (*wu wei er zhi*), emphasizing spontaneity and naturalness in artistic creation while avoiding artificiality, allowing viewers to experience the boundlessness of the Tao through meditation. This calls to mind the Zen Buddhist Sixth Patriarch Huineng's teaching: "taking no-thought as the essence, no-form as the body, and non-abiding as the basis," advocating intuitive enlightenment beyond the subject-object dichotomy. Compared to the Taoist path of losing the self, Zen Buddhism goes further: not only dissolving the attachment to self but also negating attachment to phenomena, directly pointing to the original absence of anything—the wondrous existence

within emptiness. Additionally, the painting's open and spacious composition and its treatment of void-substance dynamics can be linked to perspectives in phenomenological aesthetics: it emphasizes the participatory nature of the viewer's perception, using abstract forms to stimulate multi-layered experiences and interpretations, thereby transcending traditional representational paradigms and guiding the viewer into an open, multidimensional aesthetic field. As art historian Gao Minglu observed: "Zao Wou-Ki's painting seeks traces of existence within nothingness."¹³ This non-being is not emptiness, but rather embodies a philosophical significance akin to Heidegger's concept of *das Nichts*—a horizon that allows beings to manifest. Through abstract forms, Zao Wou-Ki's paintings translate the ontological difference into visual language; they do not depict specific beings, but instead reveal the primordial state of Being through the interplay of color and space.

This paper argues that there exists a significant divergence between the Taoist practice of losing the self and Heidegger's concept of *Dasein* in their approaches to disclosing Being. Heidegger's *Dasein*, as a distinctive

being-in-the-world, remains intrinsically tied to the world and seeks to reveal the meaning of Being through analyzing its own existential structures. However, this method still retains a trace of subjectivity—Dasein is the clearing where meaning emerges, the witness to Being. In contrast, the Taoist loss of self goes further: it completely relinquishes the subjective stance, allowing Being to manifest itself spontaneously in a state of absence of self and objects. This distinction becomes particularly vivid in the realm of art. In *The Origin of the Work of Art*, Heidegger analyzes Vincent van Gogh's painting *A Pair of Shoes*, arguing that it does not merely depict a pair of shoes but, through their wear and texture, discloses the lifeworld of the peasant woman—the soil, labor, and daily hardships.¹⁴ This interpretation emphasizes how art, through the lived experience of Dasein, reveals the truth of Being. In contrast, Taoist aesthetics proposes the concept of shooting without shooting (bu she zhi she): true artistry is like the archer Hou Yi, who, when his skill reached its zenith, no longer focused on the target or himself but instead set aside his bow and arrow, comprehending the heavenly Tao in a state of no-mind and no-thought. This state dissolves the boundary between subject and object, allowing the manifestation of Being to emerge as a natural effusion rather than a construct of the subject.

A deeper resonance lies in the philosophical interpretations of nothingness shared by Heidegger

and Taoism. In *What Is Metaphysics?*, Heidegger boldly proposes that nothingness (das Nichts) is not an empty void but rather the horizon through which Being discloses itself. He criticizes the limitations of science, arguing that science wishes to know nothing of nothingness, as it remains fixated on specific beings while ignoring the significance of nothingness as the background against which Being manifests. Heidegger contends that it is precisely the presence of nothingness that allows beings to emerge from chaos and enter our field of vision.¹⁵ This understanding of nothingness forms a striking intertextuality with the thought of the *Tao Te Ching*. In Chapter 11, Laozi writes: “Clay is molded to form a vessel, yet it is the emptiness within that makes it useful. Doors and windows are cut to form a room, yet it is the emptiness within that makes it usable.” He illustrates this principle with examples from daily life: the rotation of a wheel depends on the emptiness between its spokes; the utility of a room arises from its inner void; the function of a vessel stems from the nothingness it contains. Here, nothingness is not mere absence but the root from which beings derive their efficacy. Whether in Heidegger's nothingness or Laozi's nothingness, both point to a shared insight: the truth of Being is not an accumulation of beings but must reveal itself within the cognitive margins—the blank spaces of understanding. The Japanese philosopher Kitarō Nishida, in *An Inquiry into the Good*, further

Figure 3. Zao Wou-Ki, *Untitled*, 1972, paper, India ink, 69×119cm.

synthesized Heideggerian and Taoist thought by proposing the logic of the place of absolute nothingness (zettai mu no basho). He argued that the truth of Being relies neither on the intentional constructions of the subject nor on the ready-made attributes of the object. Instead, it blossoms spontaneously within the primordial encounter where subject and object are not yet differentiated.¹⁶ Nishida's absolute nothingness attempts to transcend the Western philosophical tradition of subject-object dichotomy, returning to a direct, pre-reflective experience of Being. This thought not only opens new pathways for dialogue between Eastern and Western philosophy but also deepens our understanding of nothingness—it is not a negative negation but a field brimming with potentiality, allowing Being to reveal itself in its authentic manner.

To further enrich this discussion, we may turn to how Heidegger, in *Being and Time*, unfolds the question of Being through the analysis of Dasein. He argues that Dasein differs from other beings in its unique capacity to always already be In-der-Welt-sein, forming an inseparable whole with its surrounding world and things. By examining Dasein's existential conditions—such as “Sorge” and “Sein-zum-Tode”—Heidegger reveals the temporal structure of Being: it is not static but unfolds dynamically through the interplay of past, present, and future.¹⁷ This emphasis on temporality bears a striking parallel to the imagery of the Roc spreading its wings in Zhuangzi's *Free and Easy Wandering (Xiao Yao You)*. The Roc, as depicted by Zhuangzi, transcends its finite form and spatial constraints, attaining a state of freedom in unity with the Tao—a freedom that embodies the spontaneous unfolding of Being itself, rather than any deliberate pursuit by a subjective self.¹⁸ This freedom is precisely the spontaneous unfolding of Being itself, rather than a deliberate pursuit by the subjective self. In the dimension of art, Heidegger further illustrates how artworks serve as a clearing for the disclosure of Being through the example of the Greek temple. He contends that the temple is not merely an architectural structure; rather, through its stance upon the earth, it unveils the world of the ancient Greeks—an intricate fusion of the divine, nature, and human existence.¹⁹ Similarly, the Taoist philosophy of non-action yet nothing is left undone (wu wei er wu bu wei) expresses a parallel idea: true action does not impose itself upon the world but aligns with the natural movement of the Tao, allowing all things to be accomplished spontaneously through non-action. This reverence for and attunement to Being, emerging at the confluence of Eastern and Western thought, holds profound significance.

Turning to Zao Wou-Ki's 1968 work *18.3.68* (figure

4), the limited canvas space evokes an infinitely expansive psychic landscape of nature. Zao creates a mysterious world that stirs the soul, inviting viewers to immerse themselves ethereally in its artistic conception—where cherry blossoms scatter like snow and falling petals merge with the earth.

Zao Wou-Ki's artistic journey evolved from figurative landscapes and still lifes in the late 1940s to early 1950s, transitioning to lyrical abstraction from the mid-1950s to early 1960s. After over a decade of exploring abstract art, his style reached full maturity by the late 1960s, characterized by a harmonious integration of color, spatial division, and brushwork, achieving a sense of compositional completeness. Created in 1968, *18.3.68* is one of the smaller works from Zao Wou-Ki's late-1960s period, yet it demonstrates meticulous spatial organization and rich layering. This carefully constructed space, through its subtle simplicity, evokes the monumental grandeur of vast mountains and oceans. As Zao Wou-Ki's imagery increasingly diverged from specific landscape references, what emerged was the inner mental landscape of his mind. He once remarked “Every painter's creation is realistic to themselves; it is only abstract to the viewer.”²⁰ The artist transforms the spatial imagery of nature into a sealed world within the frame—a world imbued with the sun, stars, and moon. All that humanity needs begins with a single point. Zao Wou-Ki masterfully employed round and filbert brushes to delineate lines: the moment the brush tip touches the canvas, a point is born; points connect to form lines, and lines coalesce into planes. *18.3.68* differs slightly from the ridge-centered composition characteristic of his early 1960s works.²¹ Its foundational structure lies in the convergence of looseness—Zao Wou-Ki used sharp, fragmented, and rapid brushstrokes to coalesce and collide the mental imagery within his mind. On the right side of the canvas, a forceful horizontal stroke in blue-black overlaps thin, rainbow-like layers of pale blue oil paint, while deep washes and fine ink-like strokes intertwine into a realm of chaos. This chaos connects leftward to a circular form at the center of the composition. This circle serves as the visual focal point against the conflict, guiding the viewer to observe countless interlaced lines with heightened clarity—lines that obscure, merge, dissolve, or interfere with one another. Like atomic nuclei of lesser mass colliding, they release tremendous energy, first pushing the surrounding elements outward and then blurring them, ultimately forming a heavier, larger circle. The center of this circle appears as negative space, yet the edges of the canvas suggest infinite extension. This effect, reminiscent of nuclear fusion—gathering and then expanding—releases

immense energy across the painting. Qi, ethereal and circular brushstrokes form the foundation of the work. It is not static; beyond gathering and dispersing, it embodies the concepts of beginning and end, becoming an indispensable element in the spatial structure. In Zao Wou-Ki's works of the 1960s and 1970s, spatial composition consistently takes precedence over color. As mentioned earlier, the circular central structure also makes it difficult for viewers to distinguish the left-right orientation or axial center of the painting, thereby generating multiple viewpoints. The shifting between these viewpoints naturally produces a pulsating kinetic energy, generating a continuous circulation of qi. In contrast, post-war European Lyrical Abstraction also emphasized the expression of the artist's emotions,

known for its spontaneous application of oil paint. In Sam Francis's *Untitled* (figure 5), the oil paint is similarly thin and filled with numerous dispersed viewpoints, yet its relatively regular brushstrokes fail to achieve the transcendent fluidity and ethereal dynamism found in Zao Wou-Ki's work. Zao Wou-Ki's painting transcends mere abstraction—it becomes a cosmic breath, a visual symphony of energy and void.

The ethereal quality in Zao Wou-Ki's work stems from the Eastern expression of restrained emotion and the artist's deep affinity for Chinese ink painting and nature. Zao Wou-Ki once remarked "The rhythm created by the interplay of void and substance in Chinese painting—a dynamic interplay where one element pushes another in continuous movement—lends the

Figure 4. Zao Wou-Ki, *18.3.68*, 1968, oil on canvas, 95×105cm.

Figure 5. Sam Francis, *Untitled*, 1977, acrylic and oil on paper, 75×104.1cm.

composition a sense of weighted lightness. If my paintings differ from those of Western artists, it is likely due to this distinct approach to spatial composition.”²² *18.3.68* captivates through its dynamic balance of movement and stillness—a cosmic atmosphere that transcends mere representation of landscapes, evolving instead into a meditation and sudden enlightenment toward the cosmic essence (*da xiang*). What distinguishes Zao Wou-Ki’s abstraction from Western abstract painting is his provision of a new perspective for viewing painting itself, rather than a method for contemplating environments or objects. Looking back to the late 1960s, Zao Wou-Ki began returning to tradition, experimenting with integrating more traditional painting techniques and aesthetic forms to construct his compositions. This approach created a naturally ethereal artistic conception, unifying his personal mental state with the hidden rhythms of the universe. The misty, rain-soaked ambiance in *18.3.68* evokes the spirit of Five Dynasties painter Dong Yuan’s *Clear Weather After Snow in the Flat Woods* (figure 6), which embodies “rivers and lakes of mountains and waters, winds and

rains in valleys, peaks now dim now bright, woods and clouds veiled in mist.” Dong Yuan’s landscape paintings were described as “executed with seemingly casual brushwork,” yet his profound depiction of light and shadow and his mastery of compositional coherence were remarkably precise.²³ Judging from the atmospheric effect conveyed in *18.3.68*, Zao Wou-Ki was likely influenced by the pictorial tradition initiated by Dong Yuan. In terms of compositional structure, the painting also adopts the scattered perspective technique characteristic of traditional Chinese landscape painting. The overall space is divided into three horizontal segments, while the extensive use of negative space in the upper and lower sections enhances the sense of depth, allowing the canvas to express the vast and profound realm of the cosmic natural world and achieve a deeply evocative lyrical conception. Zao Wou-Ki drew on the expressive techniques and aesthetic connotations of traditional Chinese freehand brushwork ink painting, skillfully integrating them with the forms of Western Abstract Expressionism. This fusion creates a remarkable synergy between two distinct artistic

Figure 6. Attributed to Dong Yuan, *Clear Weather After Snow in the Flat Woods*, Five Dynasties-Song Dynasty, ink and color on silk, 37.5×150.8cm.

languages, endowing the Western medium with an infinitely expansive spatial quality and an ethereal, contemplative Eastern ambiance. Whether through Laozi's enigmatic descriptions of the Tao, Zhuangzi's vivid portrayal of the loss of self, or Heidegger's profound insights into nothingness, all point toward a common direction: transcending the superficiality of beings to confront the authentic manifestation of Being itself. Zao Wou-Ki's paintings serve as a modern interpretation of this philosophical vision. In his works, natural elements such as mountains, rivers, clouds, and mist are abstracted into symbolic forms, seamlessly merging with the viewer's perception.

2. Critique of Technology: The Harmony between Nature and Being in Zao Wou-Ki's Art

In his later thought, Heidegger placed the critique of the essence of modern technology at the core of his philosophical inquiry. In *The Question Concerning Technology*, he introduced the concept of Gestell to reveal the deepest crisis of the technological age. While this term is conventionally rendered as framework or framing, its meaning extends far beyond the literal; it refers to a specific mode of existence, a cognitive pattern imposed by modern technology. Under the sway of Gestell, the world no longer reveals itself in its richness and mystery but is reduced to Bestand—a stockpile of resources readily available for deployment and exploitation.²⁴ Heidegger profoundly illustrates

this transformation through the example of the Rhine River: once celebrated in Johann Christian Friedrich Hölderlin's poetry as a symbol interwoven with nature and divinity, it is now disciplined by modern technology into a mere energy supplier for power plants, stripped of its poetic multiplicity. This instrumentalization of nature represents the fundamental concealment brought forth by Gestell.

Remarkably, Chapter 28 of the *Tao Te Ching* states: "When the Uncarved Block (pu) is divided, it becomes useful vessels." Here, the term Uncarved Block, symbolizing the primordial state of the Tao—an undifferentiated wholeness and potentiality—refers to wood in its natural, unprocessed form. However, when this Block is carved and fragmented into specific tools, its original integrity dissolves, replaced by functional fragments. This imagery of the division of the Uncarved Block resonates strikingly with Heidegger's concept of Gestell; both point to how technological existence obscures the fundamental source of Being. The German sinologist Günter Wohlfart astutely captured this cross-temporal dialogue, arguing that Heidegger and Laozi, within their respective philosophical contexts, jointly reveal how technology distances us from the essential dimension of existence.

However, despite the similarity in their critiques, their attitudes toward technology reveal subtle differences. Heidegger does not outright reject technology but acknowledges its double-edged nature: it is both the source of crisis and the potential for redemption. In his view, the danger of modern

technology lies in its establishment of Gestell as the sole mode of revealing existence, thereby obscuring other, more primordial paths of understanding. Yet, if we confront the essence of technology, it may be possible to open a path toward a freer mode of existence. In contrast, Taoism offers another approach through the dialectical principle of reversion: the movement of the Tao (*Tao Te Ching*, Chapter 40). This principle suggests that when the development of things reaches its extreme, it naturally reverses toward its opposite. Thus, even as technology fragments the Uncarved Block into utilitarian vessels, within this very movement of fragmentation lies the potential for return to wholeness. This transcendence does not entail a rejection of technology but rather seeks a path within technology itself to realign with the Tao.

Zao Wou-Ki's artistic practice offers a concrete response to this critique. His work draws inspiration from nature yet transcends mere representation, expressing nature's inner spirit through abstract forms. In *10.03.83* (figure 7), mineral-toned colors and sedimented pigment flows resemble wind stirring water, lacking definite contours yet brimming with vitality. This approach avoids reducing nature to a resource, instead allowing it to reveal itself in its authentic manner. Such an attitude aligns with Heidegger's concept of *Gelassenheit*, safeguarding the truth of Being from the encroachment of technological Gestell.²⁵ The intermingling of deep blue and purplish-black hues lacks clear boundaries, evoking the notion of indistinct and elusive, yet within it lies form (*huang xi hu xi, qi zhong you xiang*), where the vitality of the cosmos gestates

within ambiguity. The warm white luminous zone below seems to emerge naturally from the depths of the earth—not intentionally illuminating, yet inherently clarifying—perfectly aligning with the artistic conception of emptiness awaiting substance (*xu er dai wu*), allowing voidness to become the foundation for all things to flourish. The black silhouette-like lines, reminiscent of mountains or trees, intervene in the canvas with an attitude of non-action. They simultaneously conceal and reveal, tracing the mysterious traces of existence within the darkness. The entire painting invites viewers to immerse themselves in the surging flow of color itself. In this moment, pigment and brushstroke achieve a tacit understanding through their breath—what we see is not a re-representation of nature, but nature itself blooming in its suchness through the canvas. As Ni Zan of the Yuan Dynasty wrote in *Reply to Zhang Zaozhong*: “with untrammelled brushwork, sketchily executed without seeking formal likeness” (*yi bi cao cao, bu qiu xing si*), pushing the Taoist concept of non-action toward the Zen Buddhist perspective of contemplating emptiness (*kong guan*). His *Rongxi Studio* employs sparse, dry ink strokes to outline mountains and rocks, with vast areas of negative space symbolizing true emptiness and wondrous existence (*zhen kong miao you*)—where being is not defined by brushstrokes but emerges through the unfinishedness of broken-yet-connected intentionality. This resonates with the Zen Buddhist idea of the mind itself is Buddha (*ji xin ji fo*) in its sudden enlightenment. The flowing mineral pigments in Zao Wou-Ki's *10.03.83* echo Ni Zan's aesthetics: sedimented pigments resemble

misty clouds, while the warm white luminous zone evokes the porous cavities of Taihu rocks, using reduced brushwork (*jian bi*) to stimulate a rhythmic resonance of life. As Shi Tao proclaimed: “The painting receives ink, the ink receives the brush, the brush receives the wrist, the wrist receives the heart” (*Hua shou mo, mo shou bi, bi shou wan, wan shou xin*). This process dissolves the technological *Gestell*, allowing art to become an extension of nature’s own being.

Looking further, Zao Wou-Ki’s work also responds to the Taoist concept of Uncarved Block. In *Grey and Yellow Mountain* (figure 8), Zao Wou-Ki captures a fleeting impression of nature through minimalist composition and bold colors. His art does not instrumentalize nature but engages in a dialogue of coexistence with it. Just as Ming Dynasty artisans crafted furniture by following the natural grain of wood, Zao Wou-Ki’s paintings align with the vital rhythm (*qi yun*) of nature, allowing art to become an extension of Being. This practice is not only a reflection on the crisis of technology but also an artistic interpretation of existential harmony. The phenomenologist Klaus Held summarized this view of technology as one characterized by flexibility, inclusivity, and collaboration.²⁶ He argues that this approach offers a concrete, practical path for Heidegger’s concept of *Gelassenheit*. *Gelassenheit* is not passive submission but advocates an attitude of letting beings be, no longer imposing human dominance onto things but instead listening to and safeguarding the way things unfold in themselves. Zao Wou-Ki’s handling of ink and space exemplifies this philosophical idea—he does not attempt to conquer the medium but collaborates with it, placing both himself and the viewer within its unfolding, thereby making technique an extension of nature’s essence rather than its mere opposition.

3. The Aesthetics of Void and Whiteness: Negative Manifestation in Zao Wou-Ki’s Paintings

As mentioned earlier, Heidegger explored how artworks reveal the truth of Being through Van Gogh’s *A Pair of Shoes* (figure 9). He argued that art is not merely a representation of objects but rather, through the manifestation of the object, it opens up a world, allowing viewers to perceive deeper meanings within it.²⁷ In analyzing *A Pair of Shoes*, Heidegger employed phenomenological methods to decipher the lifeworld of the peasant woman from these shoes—how they bore the weight of the soil, the traces of labor, and the hardships of existence.²⁸ However, this paper argues that such an interpretive approach tends toward overreading.

Figure 7. Zao Wou-Ki, *10.03.83*, 1983, oil on canvas, 200×322cm.

Figure 8. Zao Wou-Ki, *Grey and Yellow Mountain*, 1950, oil on canvas, 81×100cm.

By transforming the peasant shoes into an object of philosophical speculation and imbuing them with excessive symbolic meaning, Heidegger inadvertently overlooks the simple existence of the shoes as mere things. This phenomenological overinterpretation obscures the inherent thingness of the work, failing to allow the shoes to reveal themselves in their own right. Heidegger’s dilemma lies in his attempt to capture the truth of art through language and concepts, thereby partially obscuring the autonomy of the artwork itself. In contrast, Eastern art, through the lens of Taoist aesthetics, offers a different resolution. Taoist aesthetics emphasize concepts such as non-action, naturalness, and the interdependence of being and non-being (*you wu xiang sheng*). They posit that truth is not revealed through direct exposition or detailed description but is safeguarded within nothingness and void-whiteness (*xu bai*). Here, meaning emerges not by force of interpretation but through the silent resonance of negative space—a concept vividly embodied in Zao

Wou-Ki's paintings, where emptiness breathes and formlessness speaks.

The so-called aesthetics of void and whiteness is an aesthetic paradigm rooted in classical Eastern art and philosophical traditions. Its core characteristic lies in the creation of imagery through voidness and negative space to pursue a spiritual artistic conception that transcends formal appearances. This aesthetic philosophy emphasizes mastering complexity through simplicity (*yi jian yu fan*) and containing presence through absence (*yi wu han you*). In artistic expression, it deliberately retains unfinished qualities or blank areas to stimulate viewers' imaginative participation, thereby implying infinite meaning within finite forms. It is not merely a compositional technique but a mode of contemplating the cosmos that integrates the Taoist idea of an empty room generates luminosity (*xu shi sheng bai*) and the Zen Buddhist perspective of contemplating emptiness. It

embodies an aesthetic ideal of subtlety, ethereality, and tranquility. Negative manifestation (*fu xing xian xian*) is an artistic strategy proposed in this paper. Its essence lies in indirectly outlining the presence of a subject through concealment, omission, or attenuation of the subject itself, relying instead on the surrounding environment, voidness, or non-subject elements. This strategy avoids direct imposition of meaning, instead using blank space, simplification, and suggestion to allow existence to reveal itself in a non-coercive, spontaneous manner. Eastern art forms such as painting, calligraphy, and garden design widely employ this method, using the absence of things to reflect their presence, thereby avoiding what Heidegger termed interpretive violence—an overreliance on subjective interpretation—and instead opening a horizon where Being discloses itself and truth naturally clarifies.

In Zao Wou-Ki's *6.10.1985* (figure 10), although

Figure 9. Vincent van Gogh, *A Pair of Shoes*, 1886, oil on canvas, 38.1×45.3cm.

Figure 10. Zao Wou-Ki, *6.10.1985*, 1985, triptych, oil on canvas, 280×1000cm.

brushstrokes and lines are almost entirely obscured by broad, sweeping layers of oil paint, distinct calligraphic gestures remain visible in the foreground. The triptych format, derived from Western art and often used in medieval religious paintings, conceptually symbolizes the sacred. Executing a triptych requires meticulous calculation; composition, expression, brushwork, and color deployment must all be mentally simulated before the brush touches the canvas. Moreover, the entire work measures 10 m in width and 2.8 m in height, spanning two to three times the width and twice the height of a human body. For Zao Wou-Ki, this posed immense challenges both mentally and physically, demanding tremendous willpower to complete.

6.10.1985 was created at the invitation of the renowned architect I. M. Pei. In 1952, the two met at Galerie Pierre Loeb in Paris and formed an instant connection, beginning a friendship that would last over six decades. In 1980, when Pei was commissioned for the significant Raffles City project in Singapore, he invited his close friend to create a large-scale mural for the lobby of the main tower (figures 11, 12). Zao Wou-Ki returned to France to focus on the creation, and after five months of relentless effort, completed the painting in October of the same year. *6.10.1985* was officially unveiled at the opening of Raffles City in 1986 and remained on public display until the complex underwent large-scale renovation and reconstruction in 2005. This work exemplifies the classic features of Zao Wou-Ki's boundless period: an open composition, boldly diffused and emptied, with structural solidity anchored at the peripheries to grant the central area greater spatial freedom. This reflects the artist's liberated state of mind at the time—no longer constrained by an egocentric perspective but expressing a released and liberated selfless spirituality. Jade-like shades of blue, varying in intensity, moisture, and transparency create a dynamic interplay of void and substance, emptiness

and fullness. Delicate auxiliary colors float lightly throughout, forming a spiritually resonant visual field. The overlapping brushstrokes and interwoven lines may appear chaotic, but possess a rigorous internal order and structure. As Tong Zhenguo recalled: “Watching Zao Wou-Ki revise his paintings, I noticed he rarely completed one section before moving to another. He always worked jumping and skipping, yet no matter how far apart two strokes might be, the second always had an essential connection to the first—and so did the third and fourth. Every hook and sweep, every movement back and forth, up and down, was interconnected. Despite their myriad variations, the brushstrokes were always tightly linked in momentum.”²⁹ For instance, the interlacing lines and colors in the lower right corner of the work evoke the imagery of mountain rocks and water sources in traditional landscape painting. Techniques such as texture strokes (*cun*), dotting (*dian*), and washing (*ran*)—typically executed with ink brushes—are here transformed into the twisting, lifting, and pressing movements of an oil brush. The alternating use of centered-tip and side-tip brush techniques in ink painting is reinterpreted through the hooking, pushing, sweeping, and scrubbing gestures of the oil brush. The wild, wandering thick and thin lines morph into the contour lines and texture strokes of mountain rocks. The brushstrokes resonate with one another—seemingly connected yet not entirely; the lines gaze toward each other, appearing broken yet continuous. The arrangement of strokes and lines is orderly yet dynamic, breathing with a shared rhythm. This creatively translates the rhythmic cadence of calligraphic strokes—the lifting, pressing, pausing, and turning—into oil paint, producing the unpredictable ink-wash effects of varying density, dryness, and moisture. The lines appear parched and fragmented, their quality sharp and austere, coexisting fluidity with rawness, collectively brewing a bold and powerful visual tension.

Figure 11. Zao Wou-Ki (right) and I. M. Pei, 1976.

In his *Huaguo Monk's Treatise on Painting* (*Ku Gua He Shang Hua Yu Lu*), the early Qing Dynasty painter Shi Tao proposed that “the One-Stroke is the foundation of all existence and the root of all phenomena” (*yi hua zhe, zhong you zhi ben, wan xiang zhi gen*), viewing brush and ink as the direct flow of cosmic life. This theory directly addresses the core of Heidegger’s critique of technology; while Western technology reduces nature to *Bestand*, Chinese painting asserts that brush and ink are nature itself—the artist needs only speak on behalf of mountains and rivers (*dai shan chuan er yan*). Zao Wou-Ki’s calligraphic brushstrokes constitute a modern translation of Shi Tao’s One-Stroke Theory: the dragging and dripping of oil paint do not seek to control forms but allow the material to prove its own Tao on the canvas. His treatment of negative space, compared to the traditional Chinese ink-wash practice where voidness is anchored in representational imagery, exhibits a highly non-representational abstract quality. This voidness completely breaks free from references to natural

forms, instead constructing an independent aesthetic system through pure formal language. Its internal logic remains deeply resonant with the Chinese philosophical dialectic of mutual generation of being and non-being. The highly condensed traces of brushstrokes and clusters of color on the canvas inadvertently form a visual encoding of temporal presence. When viewers engage with such works, they perceive the diachronic dimension of the creative process—an experience that, on a philosophical level, intrinsically connects with Heidegger’s emphasis on the historicity of *Dasein*—that is, *Dasein*’s understanding of its own temporal existence. This prompts viewers to touch upon the deep temporal structure of Being within their aesthetic experience.

This paper posits that Zao Wou-Ki’s aesthetics represent a critical transformation and modernist reconfiguration of the essence of traditional Chinese ink painting. On one hand, it transcends the conventional paradigm in which void space merely serves to support the representation of forms, elevating emptiness

Figure 12. *6.10.1985* exhibited at Raffles City, Singapore.

itself into an autonomous formal entity. On the other hand, through its planar abstract language, it offers a unique visual practice for addressing the Heideggerian phenomenological question of the unconcealment of Being. The core of this practice lies in its deliberate avoidance of over-technicalization and self-referential formal language. By restraining the saturated expression of pictorial elements, Zao redirects the viewer's attention to the negative spaces unoccupied by form or color. It is precisely this intentional restraint of the substantial that transforms the empty from a passive background or absence into an active phenomenological field—where non-being facilitates the manifestation of being, i.e., negative manifestation. Thus, in the realm of visual art, Zao Wou-Ki actualizes Heidegger's pursuit of letting beings be as they are, preserving the unconcealed state of the truth of Being within the artistic domain.

When Heidegger questioned the essence of things, he might have already foreseen that the truth of Being could not be captured by concepts. Shi Tao, through his One-Stroke Theory, revealed that at the moment brush and ink touch the medium Being speaks for itself. Zao Wou-Ki's paintings extend this wisdom, offering an artistic path to safeguard the truth of Being through abstraction, void-whiteness, and a profound contemplation of nature. In an era dominated by technological rationality, Zao Wou-Ki's work reminds us that great skill seems clumsy—true wisdom lies in what refuses to be spoken. His art allows us to feel the depth and mystery of existence within the interplay of color and form.

In summary, the profound dialogue between Heideggerian philosophy and Taoist thought opens a unique window into understanding Zao Wou-Ki's artistic practice. His paintings are not merely a symphony

of color and form but a clearing of the truth of Being within the visual field: by dissolving the boundaries between subject and object, they visually affirm the intrinsic resonance between Heidegger's ontological difference and the Taoist ideal of mysterious unity. Their capture of nature's spirit rather than its material appearance responds artistically to Heidegger's critique of technological Gestell and the Taoist warning against the fragmentation of the Uncarved Block into utensils (*pu san wei qi*), embodying the attitude of *Gelassenheit* that safeguards the primordial source of Being, particularly through the aesthetic strategy of negative manifestation, which leverages the power of voidness and concealment to avoid the violence of overinterpretation—Zao Wou-Ki allows Being to disclose itself spontaneously within emptiness. This not only brilliantly enacts Heidegger's principle of letting beings be but also serves as a modern translation of Laozi's wisdom that non-being confers utility (*wu zhi yi wei yong*). In an age increasingly dominated by technological rationality, Zao Wou-Ki's art resonates like an Eastern echo of great skill seeming clumsy (*da qiao ruo zhuo*)—guarding the truth of Being through visual silence and depth. Future research may further advance along the path of cross-cultural aesthetics—on one hand, exploring how different artistic media can uniquely integrate Heideggerian and Eastern wisdom, on the other clarifying the heterogeneity and complementarity of Eastern and Western thought at the ontological level of artistic creation. Ultimately, we must continue to ask how art, amid rapid globalization and digitization, can remain a poetic dwelling-place that resists forgetting and recalls authentic existence.

Sichuan University

GU ZIMO, born in Jiangsu, China, is a member of the Jiangsu Writers Association and the Nantong Literary and Art Critics Association. He has long been engaged in literary and artistic creation, with published literary and academic works totaling over 100,000 Chinese characters. He is currently pursuing studies in the Department of Art History at the College of Arts, Sichuan University.

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存在之思的東方回響——海德格爾與道家視域下的趙無極繪畫研究

顧子墨

摘 要：本文聚焦趙無極繪畫藝術，以海德格爾存在哲學與道家思想為雙重視域進行闡釋。針對當前跨文化哲學對話在藝術領域應用不足、趙無極研究多側重風格而鮮涉哲學深度的現狀，本研究旨在揭示：趙無極的抽象畫作將海德格爾的「存在論差異」與道家的「玄同」思想予以視覺化呈現，印證了藝術美學根本問題的普遍性。

關鍵詞：藝術美學；海德格爾；道德經；趙無極